

Covalently immobilized toluidine blue/sol-gel film electrode for the amperometric determination of hydrogen peroxide

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Abstract : Herein, we report our attempt to covalently immobilize toluidine blue with 3-aminopropyltrimethoxysilane and develop a simple amperometric sensor for the determination of hydrogen peroxide. The immobilization of TB to the silane matrix was effected using glutaraldehyde as the cross-linker. The mediator immobilized silane was spin coated as a thin film on a graphite rod to get the modified electrode. The modified electrode was characterized using cyclic voltammetry and its applicability as a sensor was probed for the determination of H₂O₂. H₂O₂ reduction was observed at a reduced potential of -0.33 V and a linear relation was obtained for H₂O₂ in the concentration range of 4.04×10^{-6} M to 2.81×10^{-3} M with a detection limit of 1.62×10^{-6} M and a correlation coefficient of 0.9996. Amperometric studies have revealed a rapid response at the modified electrode for H₂O₂ determinations under dynamic conditions.

Keywords : Toluidine blue, sol-gel, covalent immobilization, hydrogen peroxide.

Introduction

Achievements in sol-gel method opened larger avenues for fundamental and practical applications in the areas of material science, bioanalytical chemistry, biocatalysis, biotechnology and environmental technology^{1,2}. The attractive features of inorganic sol-gel materials include adjustable porosity, good thermal stability, chemical inertness and negligible swelling³. Sol-gel derived materials are porous and leaching of small dopants from the sol-gel matrix is a common problem^{4,5} and thus it prevents the use of sol-gel as suitable material for sensor development. This shortcoming can be overcome by covalently attaching the modifier or guest molecule to the gel framework. Functional sol-gel precursors containing -NH₂, -COOH, -SH groups facilitate the fabrication of sensing materials with possible control over the selective modification, orientation and distribution of the catalytic sites^{6,7}.

The selective and sensitive detection of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) is becoming increasingly important in the fields of biochemistry, clinical chemistry, food chemistry and environmental chemistry and so various methods have

been proposed for its determination^{8,9}. Most of the methods are complex and time-consuming while electroanalytical techniques offer useful alternatives since they allow rapid and accurate analysis. Chemically modified electrodes based on sol-gel materials have fascinated increasing attention for construction of electrochemical sensors since they allow coupling of the attractive properties of these materials to a selected redox process and thus reducing the over potential significantly^{10,11}.

In this work, we show the covalent immobilization of the water soluble mediator toluidine blue (TB) to the sol-gel matrix through glutaraldehyde crosslinking and design of a sensitive and stable amperometric sensor for H₂O₂. TB covalently bonded to the silane matrix was spin coated on graphite rod to form thin film electrode by sol-gel process. The applicability of the modified electrode as a sensor was studied using H₂O₂ as the model system.

Experimental

Toluidine blue and glutaraldehyde (25%) were obtained from S.D. Fine Chemicals. 3-Aminopropyltri-

methoxy silane (APTMOs) was obtained from Sigma Aldrich. A 50% H_2O_2 solution was purchased from Merck. H_2O_2 solution was prepared freshly everyday. The accurate concentration of H_2O_2 was determined by titration with KMnO_4 . All other chemicals were of analytical grade and used as received without purification. All solutions were made up with double distilled water. Graphite rods (5 mm diameter) of spectroscopic grade were used for modification. All electrochemical investigations were carried out with a CHI 400A Electrochemical Analyzer. Cyclic voltammetry measurements were obtained with a conventional three electrode cell with a saturated calomel reference electrode (SCE), a platinum counter electrode and the TB/sol-gel modified graphite rod serving as working electrode.

Toluidine blue was first activated with glutaraldehyde crosslinker. The crosslinking was carried out by thorough shaking of 30 mg of TB (in 5 ml of methanol) with 40 μL of glutaraldehyde (25%) for 1 h at room temperature. After this step, 100 μL of 1 M APTMOs (diluted in methanol) was added to the TB-glutaraldehyde mixture and shaking was continued for 1 more hour to complete the crosslinking of the mediator to the sol-gel matrix. This mixture was then used for the fabrication of the working electrode. Graphite rods rubbed over emery sheet and finally over velvete cloth were used. The sol-gel solution of TB immobilized to APTMOs was applied as a thin film over the electrode surface and was hand-spun to achieve a uniform coating. The rod was then allowed to stand overnight at room temperature for the polymerization and condensation of sol-gel matrix to occur. The electrode surface was washed thoroughly to remove the loosely bound mediator and used as working electrode.

Results and discussion

The primary amino group of the phenothiazine dye, toluidine blue undergoes Schiff's base reaction with one of the aldehydic groups of glutaraldehyde. When the 3-aminopropyltrimethoxy silane solution was added to this mixture, the other end of the cross-linker reacts with the terminal amino functional moiety of the sol-gel precursor. Thus the covalent crosslinking was effected through the primary amino groups of the mediator and the sol-gel precursor. The electrochemical characteristics of the

modified electrode obtained by recording the cyclic voltammogram (CV) in the potential range from 0.2 to -0.6 V at 20 mV s^{-1} in $0.1\text{ M NH}_4\text{NO}_3$ (0.05 M phosphate buffer; pH 7.00) is shown in Fig. 1 (curve c). The TB/sol-gel modified electrode exhibited a set of cathodic and anodic peaks corresponding to immobilized toluidine blue. The CV of the unmodified electrode exhibits no characteristic peaks in the range studied (curve a). The formal potential $E^{0'}$ = $(E_{\text{pa}} + E_{\text{pc}})/2$, of the immobilized mediator was found to be -0.265 V , where E_{pa} and E_{pc} are the anodic and cathodic peak potentials of the redox couple respectively. The $E^{0'}$ of immobilized toluidine blue was considerably away from that of toluidine blue free in solution (-0.210 V vs SCE) due to the covalent crosslinking of the mediator in the sol-gel matrix. A comparative study was done between the covalently immobilized sol-gel electrode and an electrode constructed by mere entrapment of the mediator in the sol-gel matrix in the absence of glutaraldehyde. The proposed strategy of mediator immobilization was effective in retaining stable electrochemical behaviour of the modified electrode in the aqueous supporting electrolyte whereas the other electrode was found to be very unstable with continuous mediator leaching in the contacting supporting electrolyte.

Fig. 1. CVs of (a) unmodified electrode, (b) $1.61 \times 10^{-5}\text{ M H}_2\text{O}_2$ at unmodified electrode, (c) TB/sol-gel modified electrode, (d) $1.61 \times 10^{-5}\text{ M H}_2\text{O}_2$, (e) $3.22 \times 10^{-5}\text{ M H}_2\text{O}_2$ at modified electrode in $0.1\text{ M NH}_4\text{NO}_3$ (0.05 M phosphate buffer : pH 7.00); scan rate : 20 mV s^{-1} .

Fig. 2. Calibration graph for the determination of hydrogen peroxide.

The feasibility of using TB/sol-gel modified electrode for the electrocatalytic determination of H₂O₂ was tested by recording the CVs of the modified electrode in 0.1 M NH₄NO₃ (0.05 M phosphate buffer; pH 7.00) in the absence and in the presence of H₂O₂. The data comparing the response of the unmodified and the modified electrode are shown in Fig. 1. In the absence of H₂O₂ a pair of well-defined redox peaks were observed at the modified electrode ascribed to the electroactivity of immobilized toluidine blue. Upon every addition of H₂O₂ there was a drastic increase in the cathodic peak current and this is due to the strong electrocatalytic effect. Under the same experimental conditions the direct reduction of H₂O₂ at the unmodified electrode shows poor response in the complete potential range studied. This shows that the direct reduction of H₂O₂ is not favoured at the unmodified electrode. Thus the modified electrode exhibited good sensitivity towards H₂O₂ reduction relative to the unmodified electrode due to electrocatalysis of the immobilized mediator. The peak current for the reduction of H₂O₂ appears at the formal potential of the immobilized TB showing the typical mediated electrocatalytic effect. The electrocatalytic activity of the modified electrode allowed the appropriate detection of H₂O₂ at lower potentials with high sensitivity.

The applicability of the present method as an analytical tool for the determination of H₂O₂ was examined by measuring the catalytic current as a function of concentration of H₂O₂. A characteristic calibration measurement for the addition of aliquots of analyte yields the direct dependence of the measured current with the concentration of H₂O₂. Fig. 2 shows a good linear relation between catalytic current and concentration of H₂O₂ in the range of $4.04 \times 10^{-6} M$ to $2.81 \times 10^{-3} M$ with a detection limit of $1.62 \times 10^{-6} M$ and correlation coefficient of 0.9996.

In order to examine the response characteristics of TB/sol-gel electrode a constant potential voltammetry was done for the detection of H₂O₂. A typical chronoamperogram was recorded for successive additions of 0.5 ml of $6.88 \times 10^{-4} M$ H₂O₂ to a 90 ml stirring supporting electrolyte solution of 0.1 M NH₄NO₃ (0.05 M phosphate buffer; pH 7.00) at a fixed potential of -0.33 V. The sensor exhibited rapid and sensitive response to changes in H₂O₂ concentration producing steady-state signals within 4 s. The nearly equal current steps for each addition of H₂O₂ shown in Fig. 4 demonstrate the efficient electrocatalytic behavior of the modified electrode for

Fig. 3. Hydrodynamic voltammograms of $1.61 \times 10^{-5} M$ H₂O₂ at (a) bare electrode and (b) TB/sol-gel modified electrode in 0.1 M NH₄NO₃ (0.05 M phosphate buffer : pH 7.00); stirring rate : 300 rpm.

Fig. 4. Current-time response observed with the TB/sol-gel electrode for successive addition of 0.5 ml of 0.7 mM H_2O_2 to 90 ml of electrolyte at -0.33 V; stirring rate : 300 rpm. Inset : Calibration plot for H_2O_2 measurement.

H_2O_2 reduction in dynamic conditions too. Such a quick and efficient response may be attributed to the fast electrocatalytic reduction occurring at the thin film electrode. The variation of catalytic current as a function of H_2O_2 concentration is drawn as a calibration curve and the range 3.80×10^{-6} M to 3.28×10^{-5} M H_2O_2 with a correlation coefficient of 0.9996 and is shown as inset to Fig. 4. The stable and sensitive reduction of H_2O_2 under dynamic condition is proving the electrode's potential application to flow systems.

Conclusion

Immobilization of TB through cross-linking to silica matrix via glutaraldehyde has been achieved successfully

and the modified sol-gel matrix has been used for developing amperometric sensor for H_2O_2 . The present work demonstrates that the TB/sol-gel film electrode enables the electroreduction of H_2O_2 to proceed efficiently at significantly lesser potential with higher sensitivity and lower detection limit. Moreover, due to the linear dependence of H_2O_2 reduction current to its concentration in a wide dynamic range, the possibility of H_2O_2 quantitation in stirred and unstirred solutions was shown using amperometry and voltammetry respectively. Also, the TB/sol-gel film electrode possessed excellent stability and reproducibility that results from robust covalent immobilization of the mediator in the mechanically rigid sol-gel support.

References

1. D. Avnir, S. Braun, O. Lev and M. Ottolenghi, *Chem. Mater.*, 1994, **6**, 1605.
2. S. S. Kumar, K. Kwak and D. Lee, *Anal. Chem.*, 2011, **83**, 3244.
3. B. Wang and S. Dong, *Talanta*, 2000, **51**, 565.
4. T. M. Butler, B. D. MacCraith and C. McDonagh, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids*, 1998, **224**, 249.
5. M. M. Collinson, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1998, **129**, 149.
6. J. Wang, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1999, **399**, 21.
7. S. S. Kumar, K. Kwak and D. Lee, *Electroanalysis*, 2011, **23**, 2116.
8. W. Chen, S. Cai, Q.-Q. Ren, W. Wen and Y.-Di. Zhao, *Analyst*, 2012, **137**, 49.
9. S. S. Kumar, G. Baek, S. Lee, C.-H. Jun and D. Lee, *Electrochem. Commun.*, 2012, **19**, 123.
10. M. Opallo and A. Lesniewski, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 2011, **656**, 2.
11. R. N. Goyal and S. Bishnoi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2012, **51**, 205.